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Mighty Typhoon Ragasa rambles through Hong Kong: A NatHaz Brief

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Typhoon Ragasa, the strongest storm to hit the South-east part of China this year, prompted the Hong Kong Observatory (HKO) to issue a Signal No. 10 warning (highest starting 2:40 am on Sep. 23, 2025, for 11 hours (the second longest lasting Signal No. 10 warning on record in Hong Kong). The typhoon resulted in 101 injuries, 1050 fallen trees, four landslides, and 19 flooding events across Hong Kong (cr. South China Morning Post).

HKO has now integrated the LiDAR system from the Hong Kong Polytechnic University INTACT project, led by Professor Y.Q. Ni, to enhance typhoon monitoring and early warning capabilities. According to HKO, super typhoon Ragasa passed approximately 100 km south of Hong Kong. At Ogong Ping weather station (a mountain place close to the coastal), the maximum hourly mean wind speed recorded was 143.4 km/h (39.8 m/s) at 11:33 am on Sep. 24, 2025, while the 10-minute mean wind speed reached 153 km/h (42.5 m/s). The same station registered a peak gust of 212 km/h (58.9 m/s) at 7:40 am that day. Separately, a weather station in Chuandao Town (close to the landing place), Guangdong, China, reported a **peak gust of 241 km/h (66.9 m/s)** around noon on Sep. 24, 2025 (cr. HKO, CMA).

Fig.1 Huge waves from Typhoon Ragasa shattered the glass doors of The Fullerton Ocean Park Hotel (cr. Bosco Chu). Video can be found:

<https://www.facebook.com/share/v/17HHQJN8kj/>

The typhoon passed through the Luzon Strait, which separates Taiwan and the Philippine island of Luzon, gaining strength as it tracked westward toward South China. In response, the Shenzhen government evacuated 400,000 people. Approximately 600 flights were canceled on Tuesday for Hong Kong International Airport (cr. BBC).

Fig. 2 (a) Track of super typhoon Ragasa (cr. HKO); (b) Urban flooding in HK after typhoon Ragasa (cr. AP News); (c) A fallen tree at Ho Man Tin, HK (cr. Ming Pao).

(a) A woman waits for rescue on a rooftop in Hualien, Taiwan (cr. AFP).

(b) Glass windows at a restaurant along the Tseung Kwan O were broken by strong winds (cr. China New Service).

(c) The exterior wall cladding of a luxury residential building at Bayshore Towers in Sham Tseng was torn off (cr. HK01).

(d) A luxury yacht in Sai Kung was nearly submerged during super typhoon Ragassa (cr. Sing Tao Daily).

Fig 3. Damages caused by Super Typhoon Ragasa across HK and Taiwan.